

Marketing strategy of Tra Vinh Pharmaceutical Joint Stock Company in 2023-2024: A 4P-based analysis

Chiến lược ‘marketing’ của Công ty Cổ phần Dược phẩm Trà Vinh năm 2023-2024:
Phân tích theo mô hình ‘marketing’ hỗn hợp 4P

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Abstract

Introduction: As Vietnam's pharmaceutical sector experiences rapid growth and heightened competition, the need for effective marketing strategies is paramount. This study addresses a gap in the existing literature by offering a detailed 4P-based analysis of the marketing strategies of a key local player, Tra Vinh Pharmaceutical JSC (TV.PHARM), from 2023 to 2024.

Methods: The study used a descriptive, retrospective design to analyze the marketing activities of TV.PHARM's product lines from January 2023 to December 2024. Data were collected from TV.PHARM's internal reports, corporate publications, and secondary industry sources. The analysis was guided by marketing-mix theory (4P), with data processed using Excel and Word. The findings are presented descriptively, supported by tables and figures.

Results and discussion: Findings show that TV.PHARM offers a broad product portfolio across multiple therapeutic areas, including nine formulations under its Travicol brand. The company applies product lifecycle management, as illustrated by the relaunch of Suspengel with improved packaging and taste. Its pricing strategy combines competitive generic pricing with frequent trade promotions, helping to increase distribution volume. The company's nationwide network includes 3 factories, 22 branches, and over 25,000 points of sale. Digital channels such as mobile apps and e-commerce platforms have been adopted to enhance reach. Promotion integrates push-and-pull. Activities in 2024 included

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school health programs, flood-relief donations, medical conference sponsorships, and social media outreach. These strategies contributed to strong growth—for example, +42.2% new customers in Khánh Hòa province.

Conclusion: TV.PHARM's cohesive marketing mix demonstrates effective implementation of the 4Ps in Vietnam's pharmaceutical context and provides a model for other firms in the industry.

Key words: marketing mix (4Ps); pharmaceutical marketing; generic pricing; distribution channels; push vs. pull strategy; Tra Vinh Pharmaceutical.

Tóm tắt

Giới thiệu: Ngành dược phẩm Việt Nam đang phát triển nhanh và cạnh tranh cao. Nghiên cứu này phân tích chiến lược marketing của Công ty CP Dược phẩm Trà Vinh (TV.PHARM) trong các năm 2023-2024 theo mô hình 4P.

Phương pháp: Dữ liệu được thu thập dựa trên thông tin báo cáo của các bộ phận chức năng của công ty và báo cáo ngành và phân tích dựa trên các mô hình marketing thông dụng.

Kết quả và bàn luận: Kết quả cho thấy danh mục sản phẩm của TV.PHARM rất đa dạng, nổi bật là 9 sản phẩm trong dòng Travicol (5 sản phẩm chứa paracetamol đơn chất và 4 dạng phối hợp). Công ty thực hiện quản lý chu kỳ sống sản phẩm, điển hình là việc cải tiến sản phẩm *Suspengel* về bao bì và hương vị. Chiến lược giá kết hợp giữa giá cạnh tranh với chương trình khuyến mãi thường xuyên, giúp thúc đẩy phân phối. Mạng lưới phân phối gồm 3 nhà máy, 22 chi nhánh và hơn 25.000 điểm bán, kết hợp cả kênh truyền thống và kỹ thuật số. Chiến lược xúc tiến bao gồm “đẩy” và “kéo”. Năm 2024, công ty tổ chức các chương trình chăm sóc sức khỏe học đường, tài trợ y tế và từ thiện. Nhờ đó, số khách hàng tại Khánh Hòa tăng 42,2%.

Kết luận: Chiến lược 4P tích hợp của TV.PHARM là một mô hình hiệu quả, có thể tham khảo cho các doanh nghiệp dược khác.

Từ khóa: chiến lược marketing; sản phẩm dược; danh mục sản phẩm; chính sách giá; kênh phân phối; xúc tiến hỗn hợp; TV.PHARM.

1. Introduction

Vietnam's pharmaceutical market has been expanding rapidly, driven by rising per-capita drug consumption and growing healthcare expenditure [1-3]. After the disruptions of the COVID-19 pandemic, the industry resumed strong growth and now faces intensifying competition from multinational and foreign-invested firms [3, 4]. In this context, effective marketing strategies are crucial for domestic companies to maintain market share and achieve growth [5]. Yet there has been limited published research analyzing how local Vietnamese firms apply marketing-mix strategies in practice. By conducting a detailed case study of TV.PHARM for 2023-2024, this study fills a gap in the literature and contributes new insights into pharmaceutical marketing strategy in emerging markets. It provides an empirical example of how the four Ps (product, price, place, promotion) are managed in a rapidly evolving industry.

TV.PHARM, established in 1992 and corporatized in 2003, is a leading Vietnamese pharmaceutical manufacturer headquartered in Trà Vinh. The company was among the first in Vietnam to adopt international standards such as GMP-WHO, GSP, and GDP, and pioneered modern soft-gel capsule production. By 2023, TV.PHARM had diversified into pharmaceuticals, herbal products, medical equipment, and non-alcoholic beverages. It has consistently ranked among Vietnam's top ten pharmaceutical firms. Analyzing TV.PHARM's marketing strategy provides insights into effective practices within Vietnam's evolving pharmaceutical industry [6]. The present study examines TV.PHARM's marketing strategies during 2023-2024 with respect to the marketing mix. Specifically, we analyze the company's product portfolio development, pricing and promotion policies, distribution (place) network, and pull/push promotional activities, considering how these elements align with market conditions. The goal is to assess the

effectiveness of TV.PHARM's marketing approach and identify successes and challenges. By systematically documenting what has worked, the study also provides a reference model for other Vietnamese pharmaceutical companies. In doing so, it offers guidance for firms seeking to adapt a balanced 4P strategy; indeed, industry leaders like DHG Pharma have maintained long-term success through similarly integrated approaches to product, pricing, place, and promotion [7, 8]. The insights from TV.PHARM's case can thus inform best practices and strategic decisions at peer companies in the sector.

2. Methods

A descriptive retrospective study was conducted using company data and industry sources covering the period January 2023 through December 2024. Data were collected from internal reports of TV.PHARM, corporate publications (annual reports, marketing plans, product catalogs), and secondary sources (industry databases, regulatory filings). The unit of analysis is the set of marketing activities for TV.PHARM's product lines during 2023-2024. The research design is non-interventional and observational.

Data collection involved extracting information on product portfolios, pricing schedules, distribution networks, and promotional programs. Sources included TV.PHARM's official documents (reports, product lists, pricing announcements) and relevant government or regulatory data on pharmaceuticals. Marketing theory guided the analysis: tools were used to contextualize findings. Marketing-mix theory (4P) provided the framework for organizing results. Data processing was performed in Excel and Word (charts, tables, descriptive statistics). Findings are presented descriptively, supported by tables and figures summarizing key data points.

3. Results

TV.PHARM implements an integrated marketing strategy based on the 4P model to expand market reach and enhance brand recognition (Figure 1). Its product portfolio is diversified in both breadth and depth, supported by competitive pricing and flexible promotional programs. Distribution spans nationwide through 22 branches and digital platforms, while promotion combines push-and-pull tactics via trade incentives, CSR, and multi-channel communication.

Figure 1. Marketing strategy based on the 4P model of TV.PHARM

3.1. Product strategy

Portfolio breadth (width): TV.PHARM's products are organized into numerous

therapeutic categories, reflecting a broad portfolio. The company divides its product offerings by therapeutic function, including

nutritional supplements (“Phariton” group, “Euca” group), respiratory treatments (Bromhenxin 8 mg, Dextromethorphan 15 mg), cardiovascular/diabetes medications (Losartan 50 mg, Metformin 1000 mg), analgesics and antipyretics (“Travicol” group), antibiotics (Beta lactam group), gastrointestinal drugs (Omeprazol 40 mg, Suspengel), anti-allergy (Cetirizin 10 mg, Desloratadin 5 mg, Fexofenadin 60mg), neurological/cerebral circulation (Flunarizin 5mg, Piracetam 800mg, Cinnarizin 25mg), anti-inflammatory/analgesic (Alphachymotripsin 4.2 mg, Prednisolon 5 mg, Meloxicam 7.5mg), and others (Distribution group). For example, the antibiotic category includes multiple classes. This diverse range allows TV.PHARM to address various market segments and manage brand investment by therapeutic line.

Portfolio length (line extension): Within each category, the company maintains a line of related products. As an illustration, the Beta-lactam antibiotic line comprises at least 12 products (Cefadroxil 500mg, Cefodoxim 100/200mg, Cephalexin 250/500mg, Cefdinir 100/300mg, Cefuroxim 250/500mg, Cefixim 250/500mg, Ceftriaxone 1g). These range from common oral antibiotics to injectable forms, covering high-demand generics. TV.PHARM has specifically focused on generics with large market potential and has invested in bioequivalence studies to ensure quality. This approach both meets local demand and complies with procurement requirements, reinforcing TV.PHARM’s competitiveness against branded imports.

Figure 2. Product strategy of Travicol

Portfolio depth (variety per product line): The company also emphasizes product depth by offering multiple dosages and formulations of key products. A prime example is the ‘Travicol’ analgesic line, which contains Paracetamol as the active ingredient. The Travicol line includes multiple dosage strengths (150mg, 250mg, 325mg, 500mg, 650mg) and various delivery

forms (coated tablets and oral suspensions). For instance, Travicol 150 and 250 are oral suspensions for children, while Travicol 325, 500, and 650 are coated tablets for adults. In total, nine products containing Paracetamol are shown in Figure 2. Moreover, TV.PHARM has developed combination formulas that pair Paracetamol with other actives: e.g., Travicol

Flu (Paracetamol 500mg + Dextromethorphan 15 mg + Loratadine 5 mg) for flu relief, Travicol PA (Paracetamol 325 mg + Ibuprofen 200 mg) for enhanced analgesia and Travicol Extra (Paracetamol 500 mg+ Caffeine 65 mg). This depth strategy ensures that customers have options for age, dosage and symptom profiles.

Figure 2 demonstrates this diversity: it shows Travicol products with paracetamol alone (150 mg through 650 mg) and combination products.

The company’s commentary highlights that offering multiple dosages allows physicians to tailor treatment by age, weight, and symptom severity. Most of these products are film-coated tablets (convenient for adults), with some suspensions for pediatric use. The depth strategy thus maximizes the potential of core active ingredients (e.g. paracetamol) through varied formulations, as reflected in clinical and consumer needs.

Figure 3. Product renovation of Suspengel from 2014 to 2024

(A) Visual comparison of the original (2014) and updated (2024) product versions, highlighting the modernized packaging and refreshed branding. (B) Summary of improvements including unchanged active ingredients, updated packaging design, and enhanced taste to improve user experience.

Product life-cycle management: TV.PHARM periodically updates key products to sustain sales. For example, in 2024 the company relaunched Suspengel (an antacid suspension) in a new generation (Figure 3A). The reformulated Suspengel retained the original active ingredients (aluminum/magnesium hydroxides, simethicone) but featured modernized packaging and improved taste (Figure 3B). This

new version was aggressively marketed nationwide with a goal of "covering over 8,000 outlets". The relaunch involved extensive promotional campaigns to raise awareness of the upgraded product. By refreshing its mature products, TV.PHARM prolongs their life-cycle and reinforces brand presence in pharmacies and clinics (note: the company uses push-and-pull methods to support such rollouts).

3.2. Pricing strategy

Table 1. Promotional programs implemented by TV.PHARM in 2024

No.	Program name	Purchase volume	Bonus ratio	Notes
1	Regular Promotional Program	Unlimited	4 + 1	Applied to all product groups. Orders can be accumulated throughout the month.
2	“Thần Tài AIKYA Knocks” Campaign	> 1,000,000 VND	20%	Applied in addition to the regular program. Gifts may include medicine, supplements,

No.	Program name	Purchase volume	Bonus ratio	Notes
				lucky money envelopes, phone cards, gold, etc.
3	32nd Anniversary Celebration of TV.PHARM	Unlimited	22 + 10	Applied to all product groups. Gifts are given directly with each order.
4	“Spread the Red of Travicol” Campaign	Unlimited	4 + 1	Gifts provided with each order, along with lucky draw coupons.
5	Mid-Autumn Festival Promotion	> 800,000 VND	15%	Still applies the regular promotion. Orders above 1 million VND receive a mooncake gift.
6	Women's Day Special “More Beauty, More Offers”	With detailed product list	Various (1+1, 2+1)	- 1 Phariton Detox + 1 Saforin DDVSPN - 1 TPBVSK E400 + 1 Saforin DDVSPN - 2 Saforin DDVSPN + 1 Saforin DDVSPN - 2 Cyfein Makeup Removers + 1 Saforin DDVSPN
7	Travicol Campaign - “Drive Home a Car”	Unlimited	4 + 1	Accumulated orders converted into lucky draw coupons.
8	Travicol Campaign - “Trip to Ba Den Mountain”	> 20,000,000 VND	20%	Still applies the regular program. Orders ≥ 20 million VND get a travel gift. Smaller orders may receive gifts like rice or phone cards.

TV.PHARM primarily adopts stable pricing aligned with generic market norms, but aggressively supplements it with promotional programs. Across 2023-2024, the company implemented a series of trade promotions to incentivize wholesalers, distributors and pharmacies. These include bonus schemes, discounts, and gifts tied to purchase volumes. Table 1 lists major promotions deployed in 2024. Other promotions (not exhaustively listed) included holiday-themed incentives (e.g., Mid-Autumn Festival, Women’s Day) with gift items like mooncakes or health supplements. The pricing strategy leverages push incentives to distributors/retailers: by offering free goods or discounts based on volume, TV.PHARM drives stocking of its products. These promotions are often stackable (e.g. a 20% discount plus participation in the regular 4+1 program) to maximize appeal. Importantly, such programs are time-bound and vary by season, allowing flexibility and cost control.

TV.PHARM’s products are more competitively priced than other companies, making it easier to penetrate new markets and expand distribution networks, bringing products closer to people in rural areas and middle-income groups. For example, according to the listed price of Long Chau distribution system: Active ingredient Atorvastatin (reduces blood cholesterol): Atorvastatin 20mg TV. Pharm (640 VND/tablet). Lipvar 20 DHG Pharma (2,600 VND/tablet). Active ingredient Metformin (Treatment of diabetes): Metformin 850mg TV.PHARM (800 VND/tablet), Metformin Stella 850mg (967 VND/tablet), Glumeform 850 DHG (1,200 VND/tablet).

In addition to promotions, TV.PHARM maintains competitive reference pricing. Many products are generics, so prices are set to be attractive relative to brand-name equivalents (some comparisons of product prices with competitors are documented in internal reports). For proprietary or value-added products (like the

nutraceutical Phariton line), the company sometimes uses “value pricing” - placing them at a premium justified by unique formulations. Overall, the mix of stable list prices with dynamic promotional tactics helps the company manage revenues while encouraging channel loyalty.

3.3. Distribution strategy (place)

TV.PHARM’s distribution network is comprehensive. The company operates 03 manufacturing facilities in Tra Vinh: one each for non-beta-lactam drugs, beta-lactam drugs, and nutraceuticals. The corporate headquarters is in Tra Vinh, with a representative office in Hanoi. It maintains 22 branch offices across Vietnam, responsible for regional sales and distribution. These branches service a vast network of retail outlets. As of 2024, TV.PHARM had approximately 25,358 points of sale nationwide (spanning all 63 provinces). These include hospitals, clinics, chain pharmacies, private drugstores and independent retailers. In addition, TV.PHARM exports products to various countries in Asia (Laos, Mongolia, several ASEAN nations) and Africa (Nigeria, Somalia, Yemen). This indicates a modest but strategic international presence.

Distribution follows a mix of direct and indirect channels. The company’s own sales force (via branch offices) works directly with large institutional buyers (hospitals, chains) while also servicing wholesalers and distributors. These intermediaries then supply smaller pharmacies and retailers. Notably, indirect channels (wholesalers and distributors) dominate in many regions, enabling broad market penetration with manageable logistics. Recent performance data illustrate the network’s effectiveness. In Phú Yên, retailers increased modestly (+7.3%), while in Khánh Hòa city they jumped +42.2% (from 358 to 509 customers). Overall regional customers grew +30.5%. This sharp growth in Khánh Hòa

suggests untapped market potential and effective distribution expansion. The report notes this as evidence that “distribution and marketing policies... are on the right track”.

TV.PHARM aligns its strategy with sustainable growth for customers and communities, reflected in promotional and community initiatives. Its “TV.PHARM store” mobile app, part of its digital transformation, shares core functions with DHG’s “Cung Think Vương” app (online purchasing, order tracking, financial management, product information, promotions, and customer support) while differing slightly in interface and specific features. It also established official online stores on e-commerce platforms (Shopee, Tiki), allowing customers to buy products online. Notably, orders from Khánh Hòa area placed online are fulfilled directly by the branch, ensuring quick delivery. This omni-channel approach (merging traditional sales force with digital commerce) extends reach, especially to modern consumers and remote areas. In summary, TV.PHARM’s place strategy is to maintain a wide and dense coverage. With multiple factories and branches, it ensures product availability throughout Vietnam. The channel mix (direct sales force plus regional distributors and e-commerce) enhances convenience for customers. Such a structure supports the company’s goal of high market coverage and rapid delivery, which is critical in pharmaceuticals.

3.4. Promotion strategy

TV.PHARM employs both *pull* and *push* promotional tactics to drive demand. Pull strategies are aimed at end-users and general public (to build brand awareness and demand), while push strategies target trade partners (to encourage stocking and selling TV.PHARM products).

As noted, the company's promotional pricing programs (Figure 4A) are push-oriented, rewarding distributors and retailers. In addition, TV.PHARM conducts personal selling and trader support through its sales teams. Representatives organize on-site training and

detailing sessions at clinics and pharmacies, highlighting product benefits and usage (Figure 4B). They also provide branded materials (e.g. point-of-sale displays for Travicol) and manage inventory rotations.

Figure 4. Push-and-pull strategy

(A) Pull strategy example: Social media content and brand campaigns. (B) Schematic comparison of pull versus push strategies.

TV.PHARM actively promotes its brands to consumers and healthcare professionals through events and public relations. During 2024, the

Table 2). For example, the campaign from Apr to Dec 2024 was an educational tour visiting 40 schools in 12 provinces, featuring a mascot and distributing samples to schoolchildren. This campaign aimed to raise awareness of Travicol brand (for pediatric care) and foster positive brand associations from a young age.

Another event was the “10,000 medicine kits for flood relief” in September 2024 in northern provinces. In this, TV.PHARM donated essential medications to communities affected by flooding, enhancing public image and community ties. The company also participated

company organized numerous promotional events and CSR activities across Vietnam (

in industry exhibitions and conferences. For instance, at Pharmedi Vietnam 2024 (a major pharmaceutical expo), TV.PHARM presented its products and partnership opportunities. It sponsored scientific events such as the 2nd Vietnam-American Neurology Symposium in Vĩnh Long (Jul 2024) and the HCMC Pharmacy Association conference (Mar 2024), thereby engaging healthcare professionals and policymakers. TV.PHARM's CSR activities are also notable pull efforts. In early 2024, the company donated VND 2 billion worth of gifts for Tet (Lunar New Year) to poor households. It

distributed health insurance cards and free medical check-ups in Trà Vinh, and organized “Warm Tet” programs in mountainous provinces (Lai Châu, Thanh Hóa). These humanitarian gestures reinforce the brand’s image as community-oriented and health-conscious.

Table 2. Promotional and community engagement activities by TV.PHARM in 2024

Time	Location	Activity description
Apr-Dec 2024	40 schools in 12 Mekong provinces & HCMC	“Healthy Kids with May and Travicol” school campaign
Sep 2024	Northern provinces	“10,000 Relief Medicine Packages for the Flood Season” - Solidarity with the North
Sep 2024	Saigon Exhibition & Convention Center	Partnership showcase: TV.PHARM - AIKYA member at Pharmedi Vietnam 2024
Aug 2024	Hanoi	Supporting the 2nd National Journalism Forum “For Public Health”
Jul 2024	Vinh Long	Sponsoring the Vietnam-US International Neurology Conference 2024
Jun 2024	Tho Xuan	Donated 200 million VND to Tho Xuan General Hospital
Jun 2024	Ho Chi Minh City	Kids Fest 2024 - Children’s Festival
May 2024	Online	“Healthy Stomach Advice” - Online educational session
May 2024	Livestream	“How to Manage Acid-Related Stomach Pain” - Livestream health talk
May 2024	Ho Chi Minh City	Phariton sponsored the 29th No.1 CHAMPIONSHIP sports tournament
Apr 2024	Thanh Hoa	Supported coastal fishermen with solar-powered fishing lights
Mar 2024	Ho Chi Minh City	Sponsored the 1st HCMC Expanded Pharmacy Conference 2024
Mar 2024	Tra Vinh	Provided free health insurance and medicine distribution in 2024
Jan 2024	Tra Vinh	Donated 2 billion VND in Tet gifts for low-income households
Jan 2024	Lai Chau & Thanh Hoa	“Warm Tet” program for underprivileged households in Lai Chau & Thanh Hoa

On digital and mass media channels, TV.PHARM ran consumer-oriented campaigns. For example, the *Phariton* nutraceutical line (nutritional supplements) sponsored online health seminars (“Good advice for a healthy stomach” livestreams in May 2024). The company maintains an active presence on e-commerce platforms and social media, using online ads and influencer partnerships to reach younger consumers.

Overall, TV.PHARM’s promotion mix integrates traditional marketing (educational roadshows, conference sponsorships, print media) with digital outreach (e-commerce, webinars). This multi-channel approach helps pull demand at both the consumer and professional level, complementing the push efforts of trade promotions.

4. Discussion

The analysis shows that TV.PHARM's marketing strategies are comprehensive and well aligned with industry conditions. The company's broad product portfolio ensures it meets diverse customer needs. By covering multiple therapeutic categories and offering variations in dosage and formulation, TV.PHARM reduces dependency on any single product and enhances cross-selling opportunities [9, 10]. This product differentiation creates loyalty among both doctors and patients by providing solutions for different segments (pediatric, adult, acute care, chronic care, etc.) [11].

The pricing and promotion strategy also demonstrates a balanced approach. Stable reference pricing keeps the company competitive in the generics market [5], while frequent promotional campaigns (e.g. bonus schemes and festive discounts) stimulate sales volume [12]. The regular "4+1" bonus program and seasonal promotions align well with Vietnam's distribution culture, where wholesalers and pharmacies expect volume incentives. These push-marketing tactics have clearly driven growth: for example, one provincial branch reported a +42.2% increase in customer accounts in 2024. This jump in the number of customers indicates that TV.PHARM's aggressive incentives and expanded distribution (including new digital sales channels) are yielding strong results [13]. At the same time, TV.PHARM is investing in pull marketing to build its brand. Educational campaigns and CSR events (such as school health programs and disaster relief) enhance brand equity and trust [14, 15], potentially influencing long-term customer preferences [16, 17]. Sponsorship of medical conferences and participation in industry expos also position the company as a serious player [5]. These activities complement the push programs and contribute to sustained demand [18].

TV.PHARM's distribution network performance is noteworthy. The company operates three manufacturing sites and a national network of 22 branches servicing ~25,000 retail outlets. Growth in branch sales territories indicates effective market penetration. The integration of technology - for example, a customer ordering mobile app and official online stores on e-commerce platforms - reflects forward-looking adaptation to digital trends [19, 20]. As smartphone adoption rises in Vietnam, such omni-channel capabilities help capture demand that might otherwise go to competitors or informal channels [19, 21]. Still, some challenges remain: only 22 branches cover 63 provinces, so remote areas may be underserved, and traditional promotions could be augmented with data-driven loyalty programs or CRM analytics [22, 23]. Addressing regulatory factors (such as price controls and insurance reimbursement) will also be important [24]. Continuing to build the 'TV.PHARM' brand beyond its core regions can further support long-term growth, especially in competition with imported brands.

In comparison, DHG Pharma (the largest domestic pharmaceutical company) employs similar marketing-mix strategies (diversified products, value-based pricing, strong distribution, and promotion) [7]. DHG's nationwide distribution network is recognized as the deepest in Vietnam [7], and this extensive reach has helped it maintain market leadership for over two decades [8]. For instance, DHG reported its revenue grew +16.8% in 2022 [8], reflecting steady expansion at scale. TV.PHARM's network, by contrast, is smaller, but its branch-led model has achieved rapid local gains: one branch saw a +42.2% jump in customer count in 2024. These figures illustrate that while TV.PHARM operates on a smaller scale, its aggressive push-promotions and distributor incentives yield significant growth in

targeted markets. Both companies' results align on core principles of the 4Ps: TV.PHARM's integrated strategy appears "effective and cohesive" in practice, echoing the best practices demonstrated by DHG. This comparison suggests that TV.PHARM can further enhance its approach by emulating aspects of DHG's model (for example, expanding distribution coverage and strengthening brand-building initiatives) to amplify its market impact while maintaining its agile promotional tactics.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, TV.PHARM's marketing strategy for 2023-2024 has adopted a comprehensive, 4P-based approach. The company's wide product range (across many therapeutic categories), competitive pricing coupled with targeted promotions, extensive distribution coverage (factories, branches, and e-commerce channels), and balanced use of push-and-pull promotion have together driven strong performance outcomes (such as notable customer growth). These integrated efforts align with the study's objectives and demonstrate that systematically managing product, price, place, and promotion can enhance competitiveness. TV.PHARM's case exemplifies how a cohesive marketing-mix strategy can strengthen market presence; by aligning all 4Ps in concert, the company has bolstered its position in Vietnam's pharmaceutical industry and is well positioned to sustain further growth.

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